

Quantum Flow Versus Classical MaxEnt Balance

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Maximization of entropy subject to a constraint $\sum_i P(e_i) = E_{ave}$ may be used to determine the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $\exp(-e_i/T)$, where T is temperature. In the case of a potential $V(x)$, one may maximize $-P(x) \ln(P(x))$ subject to the constraint $\int V(x)P(x)$. Average potential energy is not an a priori known value, but we have argued in the past that maximization of entropy subject to a constraint, followed by a derivative leads to a balance equation.

What about a classical mechanical bound problem? This is usually considered nonstatistical. We suggest it may be a statistical problem, but one for which maxent applies to flow, in particular the quantum bound problem. We have argued before that for a free particle, one may maximize Shannon's entropy $-P(t)\ln(P(t))$ subject to a periodic constraint $\int E_t P(t)$ and $-P(x)\ln(P(x))$ subject to $\int p_x P(x)$ to obtain $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. We argue these are associated with flows in time and space, and that there are problems in nature based on such flow and its interference.

Classically, a bound system is a flow problem because a particle moves to the right and then left, between turning points. This means the particle is confined or localized, but $\exp(ipx)$ is not. $\exp(ipx)$ is two dimensional to account for motion in a certain direction, but both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ exist everywhere in space. A bound system should not have one directional motion, on average, thus either $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ applies, i.e. a certain parity. How does one account for a probability value in all of space? We argue that in the flow $\exp(ipx)$ picture, one must consider a bound problem in equilibrium with particles trying to enter or escape. By creating an ensemble $W(x) = \sum_v a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and having $W(x)$ tend to 0 at $x = \pm\infty$ one may create such a flow picture. At first one may consider any $a(p)$ values, but we argue that either $a(p) = -a(p)$ or $a(p) = a(-p)$ for all p in this note, i.e. there is no mixing of parity. We try to show this. We then argue that $V(x)$ does not impede this flow statistics, but only imposes conditions on the average kinetic energy at x . Thus Newtonian mechanics deals only with this restriction and not with the underlying average of maxent flow probabilities $\exp(ipx)$.

A classical statistical gas is not a flow problem, but a balance problem with or without $V(x)$. Interparticle collisions change the kinetic energy of a particle and hence break its $\exp(-iet)$ flow probability. The stochasticity is then not in the flow, but in the flow-breaking collisions

We suggest that this is linked to maximization of entropy subject to a constraint and deals with different probabilities than flow ones ($\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iet)$). A Rabi frequency problem on the other hand is a flow in time problem with the magnetic field not inhibiting this flow. Finally, there may be problems which at first appear to be a balance problem, but are really a flow one, like one dimensional photon reflection/refraction.

Classical Statistical Gas

A classical gas is based on balance i.e. pressure balance in the case of no potential and pressure force balance, $\text{density}(x)RT = -dV/dx P(x)$, in the case of $V(x)$. Such a balance follows from the maximization of entropy $-P(x)\ln(P(x))$ subject to the constraint $\int V(x)P(x)$ (here the Lagrange

multiplier is fixed) followed by taking d/dx . A free physically observable parameter, namely density $NP(x)$, allows for the balance to occur. We stress that maximization of entropy subject to a real constraint leads to physically observable probabilities, unlike the flow probabilities $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-iEt)$ which are usually not considered directly observable (although some argue that soft measurements can measure a wavefunction). This feature also holds for a two level electron-nucleus system in equilibrium with absorbed/emitted photons. $P(E_0)$ and $P(E_1)$ are directly observable probabilities..

Flow Equilibrium

In general, a classical bound state problem is considered as a deterministic one with $V(x)$ fixing the kinetic energy at each x for a constant total E . This is certainly a deterministic feature but we argue a bound state problem is really associated with a flow which is associated with a special kind of maximization of entropy subject to imaginary constraints creating a periodic complex probability. The complex nature of the probability, at least in the case of $\exp(ipx)$ describes the direction of flow. As noted before, one may maximize $-P(t)\ln(P(t))$ subject to $iEtP(t)$ and $-P(x)\ln(P(x))$ subject to $-ipx P(x)$ to obtain the flow probabilities $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ with x and t being independent, but linked on average by $v=x/t$. Here we deal with a free particle. (Note: a collection of many particles may have an overall flow (fluid) but there are energy changing collisions (linked to temperature) which break the flow probabilities $\exp(-iet)$).

We ask, What happens when flow probabilities are linked with a potential $V(x)$? In the classical statistical gas one does not deal with flows and so the situation is completely different. One deals with balances. If one assumes that $V(x)$ cannot destroy the flow probabilities $\exp(ipx)$, then one might consider an ensemble.

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

$\exp(ipx)$ implies flow in one direction. If one wishes to have on average no net flow in a direction, then ((1)) must be a real quantity. $\exp(ipx)$ s, however, are orthogonal functions, and so to create a real value, one might expect it must occur at a p level i.e.

$$a(p) \exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx) = \text{real value} \quad ((2))$$

This implies that $a(p)=-a(-p)$ or $a(p)=a(-p)$. What if the first condition applies to some p and the second to others? A real result will result, but it will have mixed parity in x . In other words, parity is a property of each component of $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $\cos(px)$ has positive parity and $\sin(px)$ negative. If one component vanishes, the remaining one has a fixed parity associated with the nondirectional flow in space. We argue that this feature seems to carry over to ((2)) suggesting a collective feature of the $a(p)$'s needed to create a bound state resonance'. Simply having a real value ((2)) is not enough. Either $a(p)=a(-p)$ or $a(p)=-a(-p)$ for all p values. This creates a special kind of ensemble for ((1)) which may not at first have been apparent. In other words, average flow is chosen to preserve parity, just as each component of $\exp(ipx)$ has unique parity.

As a result, the effect of $V(x)$ is not to disturb the flow probabilities $\exp(ipx)$, but only to place a constraint on their average $pp/2m$ value at each x . It is true there is a balance linked with the resulting conservation of energy equation:

$$\text{Average KE} + V(x) = E \quad ((3)) \text{ namely } d/dx \text{ Average KE} = -dV/dx \quad ((4))$$

If maximization of entropy subject to a constraint followed by say d/dx leads to a balance, then why shouldn't one perform this procedure to find probabilities $P(p,x)$ instead of using the flow ones which force one to use ((3)) to find $a(p)$ values. Even though there is a balance equation ((4)), there is explicit flow which is not accounted for in the balance equation from maximization of entropy subject to a $V(x)P(x)$ constraint. Such an approach applies to a different physical problem, namely a flow breaking one. It seems one must identify flow in a problem (without a temperature like resonance) to use $\exp(ipx)$ s or $\exp(-iEt)$ s and their superpositions. This also means that fields in the problem do not change the flow but only influence it.

In the ensemble ((3)), flow probability exists in all of space. How can this be applied to a bound problem which is supposed to be localized between turning points? We argue that flow probabilities describe flows in all of space, so describe a bound problem with also probability for a particle to tunnel in and out of the bound region.

Examples of Flow Problems

We consider some examples of flow problems. The quantum bound problem is one as is n-slit interference. A Rabi frequency is another, although here $\exp(-iEt)$'s are used. Consider a particle with spin .5 in the x direction. A magnetic field B_z is turned on in the z direction. The wavefunction at $t=0$ is:

$$|.5 \text{ spin along } x\rangle = 1/\sqrt{2} |+\rangle + 1/\sqrt{2} |-\rangle \quad ((5))$$

The magnetic field allows for the formation of two resonances with energy $-E_0$ and $+E_0$, i.e. one has :

$$|.5 \text{ spin along } x\rangle = \exp(-iE_0 t) |+\rangle + \exp(+iE_0 t) |-\rangle \quad ((6))$$

$\exp(-iEt)$ implies maximization of entropy linked with the constraint $iEtP(t)$. The magnetic field simply creates this resonance and allows the particle to flow in time. Why isn't this the case for a two level electron-nucleus system interacting with photons? Flow in time is based on an energy eigenstate E_i , but an emitted or absorbed photon changes E i.e. breaks up the flow probability at points in time which are stochastic. In other words, there is a stochasticity not linked with flow probability $\exp(-iEt)$.

Like with ((4)), one cannot assume that whenever there is a physical balance, one may simply apply maximization of entropy and take a derivative. A one dimensional photon moving in the x direction and reflecting/refracting at an n_1 - n_2 interface along y at $x=0$ is an example. There is clearly flow in this problem, suggesting flow probabilities $\exp(ipx)$, but there is also a balance of pressure and conservation of probability $1 = P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract})$. Written in terms of fluxes, these two equations are the same:

$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ and $AAp_1 - BBp_1 = CCp_2$ ((7)) where $E=pc$ with E being the same for the incident AA , reflected BB and refracted CC photons. As a result, one cannot solve for two unknowns B, C (A known). Using flow probabilities, however, allows for the problem to be solved.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there exist flow probabilities (based on the maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to $-iEtP(t)$ and $i pxP(x)$ constraints which define periodic probabilities (in 2 dimensions) in all of space. For $\exp(ipx)$, the two dimensions indicate direction of motion.

We suggest that although maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint may apply to systems with interactions which break the E or p value linked with flow probabilities $\exp(-iEt)$ or $\exp(ipx)$, e.g. a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas which changes e_i or the absorption/emission of a photon which changes a bound state energy, there are systems which depend on flow probabilities such as a quantum bound state, a Rabi frequency situation, n -slit interference/diffraction and one dimensional reflection/refraction of a photon. as well as n -sit interference. In such a case, interactions do not break the flow probability but lead to interference of different flow probabilities.